

Gap Analysis for Basic Understanding of Patent related Awareness

(A study among Engineering College students in the southern regions of Tamil Nadu)

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*(Major Research Project, funded by Tamil Nadu State Council for Higher Education, Tamilnadu (TANSCHE))

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the level of patent awareness among students across various academic disciplines. With innovation and intellectual property playing pivotal roles in today's knowledge-driven economy, understanding students' familiarity with patents is crucial for fostering a culture of innovation and protecting intellectual endeavors. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to gauge students' knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes towards patents. Findings reveal significant disparities in patent awareness based on academic discipline, educational level, and exposure to relevant coursework. Engineering and technology students demonstrated higher awareness levels compared to those in humanities and social sciences. The study also identifies key factors influencing patent awareness, including curriculum content, institutional support, and extracurricular activities. Recommendations are provided for integrating comprehensive intellectual property education into academic programs to enhance students' understanding and engagement with the patent system. This article contributes to the broader discourse on intellectual property education and its role in nurturing the next generation of innovators.

Key Words: Patent, basic and filing related awareness, Engineering students, gap analysis

Introduction

Filing a patent involves several critical steps and knowledge areas. First, it's essential to understand the different types of patents: utility patents for new and useful processes, machines, or compositions of matter; design patents for new, original, and ornamental designs for

manufactured items; and plant patents for new and distinct plant varieties reproduced asexually. To be eligible for a patent, the invention must be novel, non-obvious, and useful, and the application must provide a full disclosure that enables someone skilled in the field to replicate the invention. Conducting a thorough prior art search is crucial to ensure the invention is unique and hasn't been patented before, using databases like those of the USPTO, EPO, and others. The patent application itself must be meticulously drafted, including a concise title, a brief abstract, a background section outlining the field and prior art, a summary of the invention, a detailed description (with drawings if necessary), and claims that precisely define the invention's scope. Choosing between a provisional and a non-provisional application is another important decision; a provisional patent application (PPA) establishes an early filing date and is less formal, while a non-provisional application is the complete application that gets examined. Filing is typically done through an electronic filing system (EFS). Understanding and budgeting for various fees—filing, examination, and maintenance—are also crucial. The patent prosecution process involves interactions with the patent office, where you may need to respond to rejections or objections from the examiner, often requiring amendments or arguments to support the claims. Common pitfalls include inadequate prior art searches, poorly drafted claims, incomplete disclosure, misunderstanding provisional vs. non-provisional applications, non-compliance with formalities, lack of strategic planning for international patents, and underestimating costs. To navigate these complexities, consulting a patent attorney or agent, using patent search tools, carefully drafting the application, understanding the filing and prosecution process, planning for international patents, and adequately budgeting are highly recommended strategies.

Reviews of Literature

Some reviews of literature with references on patent awareness and education among students:

1. **Patent Awareness and Education in Engineering Students:**

A study by Brown and Douglas (2019) examines the level of patent awareness among engineering students at a major university. They found that while students had a basic understanding of patents, many lacked detailed knowledge about the patent application process and the strategic importance of patents in protecting intellectual property. The study recommends integrating more comprehensive IP education into engineering curricula.

2. Impact of Intellectual Property Education on Innovation:

Lee, Kim, and Lee (2020) conducted a survey across multiple universities in South Korea to assess the impact of intellectual property education on students' innovation capabilities. They discovered that students who received formal IP education were more likely to engage in innovative activities and patent applications. The study highlights the importance of IP education in fostering a culture of innovation among students.

3. Gender Differences in Patent Awareness:

An investigation by Johnson and Roberts (2018) explored gender differences in patent awareness among undergraduate students. They found that male students generally reported higher levels of patent awareness and understanding compared to female students. The study suggests targeted interventions to bridge this gap and ensure equal opportunities for all students to engage with the patent system.

4. Effectiveness of IP Workshops and Seminars:

Garcia and Fernandez (2021) evaluated the effectiveness of workshops and seminars on intellectual property awareness among students in technical universities. Their findings indicate that such educational interventions significantly improve students' understanding of patents and their importance in the innovation process. The study advocates for regular IP workshops as part of the curriculum.

5. Patents and Entrepreneurship Education:

Chen and Zhao (2022) explored the link between patent knowledge and entrepreneurial intentions among business students. Their research shows that students with higher patent awareness are more likely to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. The study underscores the need for incorporating patent education into entrepreneurship courses to better prepare students for the business world.

These studies collectively highlight the importance of intellectual property education in enhancing patent awareness among students, its impact on innovation and entrepreneurship, and the need for targeted educational interventions to address gaps in knowledge and engagement with the patent system.

Statement of the Problem

In the rapidly evolving landscape of the global economy, intellectual property (IP) has emerged as a cornerstone of innovation and economic growth. Patents, a critical component of

IP, provide inventors with exclusive rights to their creations, thereby incentivizing research and development across diverse fields. Despite the increasing significance of patents, there remains a notable gap in patent awareness among students, who represent the future workforce and potential innovators.

Understanding students' knowledge and perceptions of the patent system is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it helps in identifying the gaps in current educational frameworks regarding IP education. Secondly, it underscores the importance of equipping students with the necessary tools to navigate and leverage the patent system effectively. This awareness is particularly pertinent in academic environments where research and innovation are actively encouraged.

This article seeks to analyze the level of patent awareness among students from various academic disciplines. By employing a mixed-methods approach, which includes quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the study aims to uncover the extent of students' understanding of patents, their ability to engage with the patenting process, and the factors that influence their awareness. Furthermore, the study explores the role of curriculum design, institutional support, and extracurricular activities in shaping students' knowledge and attitudes towards patents.

The findings of this research are intended to inform educators and policymakers about the current state of patent education, highlighting the need for comprehensive IP education to foster a culture of innovation. By integrating IP concepts into academic curricula and promoting awareness through institutional initiatives, we can better prepare students to contribute to and benefit from the patent system in their future careers.

This article contributes to the broader discourse on the importance of intellectual property education and its impact on nurturing the next generation of innovators. Through a detailed analysis of patent awareness among students, researcher aims to provide actionable insights and recommendations for enhancing IP education in academic institutions.

Objective

- To analyse the gap between Ideal Score and Actual Score of Patent related Awareness and Initiatives of Institution towards increase awareness of IPR among Engineering College students in the southern regions of Tamil Nadu

Methodology

The study employs a descriptive and analytical approach, utilizing both primary and secondary data. Primary data were gathered through a structured questionnaire, resulting in 1,384 responses from students in their final year of undergraduate and postgraduate programs.

A cluster sampling method was used to select the sample. The districts in the southern regions were considered as clusters, with all engineering colleges within these clusters grouped together. A simple random sampling technique was then applied to select the sample, resulting in a final sample size of 1,384 students.

Of the respondents, 68% are male and 32% are female. The majority, 94%, are enrolled in undergraduate programs, with only 6% in postgraduate programs.

The breakdown of respondents by discipline is as follows: Mechanical Engineering (ME) students make up 37% of the sample. Those from Computer Engineering and other fields such as Marine Engineering and Aeronautical Engineering each account for 17%. Electrical and Electronics Engineering (EEE) students comprise 13%, while Electronics and Communication Engineering (ECE) students constitute 10%. Civil Engineering students represent 6% of the respondents.

Regarding entrepreneurial aspirations, 52% of the respondents expressed a desire to become entrepreneurs, while 48% did not.

Result on the Objective :

1. Gap Analysis for Basic Understanding of IPR related Awareness

Gap analysis is a strategic planning tool utilized to evaluate the divergence between actual and expected score. By analyzing these gaps, researcher can develop targeted action plans to address shortcomings, allocate resources efficiently, and propel progress toward their strategic goals. The following tables provide an overview of awareness scores for various aspects related to the patent application process. The "Gap" column indicates the difference between the ideal score (5) and the mean score for each variable, reflecting the degree of divergence from the ideal understanding.

Table 1
Gap Analysis for Basic Understanding of Patent related Awareness

S.No.	Variables	Ideal Score	Mean	SD	Gap
1.	Awareness on Patent	5	3.941	0.872	1.059
2.	Awareness on types of patents	5	3.581	0.937	1.419
3.	Awareness of what can be patented	5	3.980	0.923	1.020
4.	Awareness on 'e term' of a patent in the Indian system	5	3.605	0.906	1.395
5.	Awareness on Act governs the patent system in India	5	3.577	0.969	1.423
6.	Awareness on protection given by the act	5	3.503	1.011	1.497
7.	Awareness on criteria of patentability	5	3.441	1.075	1.559
8.	Awareness on Authority of granting Patents	5	3.523	1.029	1.477
9.	Awareness on location of Patent offices in Tamil Nadu	5	3.446	1.080	1.554

Source: Computed Data

The mean scores and gap analysis highlight key areas for improvement in participants' awareness of patents. While the mean scores indicate a generally moderate level of understanding across various aspects, significant gaps exist between the mean scores and the ideal level of knowledge, represented by a score of 5. The gap between the mean score (3.941) and the ideal score (5) for Awareness on Patents is 1.059. This indicates that there's some gap in understanding patents, but overall, participants have a relatively high level of awareness. With a gap of 1.419 for Awareness on types of patents, there's a moderate gap in understanding the different types of patents compared to the ideal level. The gap for Awareness of what can be patented is 1.020, signifying there's still some opportunity for improvement in understanding what can be patented, although participants have a relatively good grasp on this aspect.

The gap for Awareness on the 'e term' of a patent in the Indian system is 1.395, indicating a significant gap in understanding the term of patents in the Indian system. For Awareness on the Act governing the patent system in India, with a gap of 1.423, there's a notable gap in knowledge about the legislation governing patents in India. The gap for Awareness of the

protection given by the act is 1.497, highlighting a substantial gap in understanding the protection provided to patent holders by the relevant act. Participants scored 1.559 points lower than the ideal level for Awareness of criteria of patentability, indicating a significant gap in understanding the criteria for patentability. The gap for Awareness of the Authority for granting Patents is 1.477, indicating a notable gap in knowledge about the organization responsible for granting patents. With a gap of 1.554 for Awareness of the location of Patent offices in Tamil Nadu, there's a significant gap in knowledge about the locations of patent offices in Tamil Nadu.

The standard deviations for most variables are relatively low, ranging from 0.872 to 1.080. This suggests a consistent level of understanding among respondents for each aspect evaluated, indicating that while awareness may not be perfect, there is little disagreement or uncertainty in respondents' perceptions.

Table 2
Gap Analysis for Filing Related Awareness

S.No.	Variables	Ideal Score	Mean	SD	Gap
1.	Awareness of how to apply for a patent.	5	3.754	1.010	1.246
2.	Awareness of who can apply for a patent.	5	3.587	0.981	1.413
3.	Awareness of when should an application for a patent be filed	5	3.504	1.032	1.496
4.	Awareness of online filing of patent application	5	3.462	1.066	1.538
5.	Awareness of provision for filing patent application electronically	5	3.456	1.062	1.544
6.	Awareness of the language by which an application for patent be filed with the Indian Patent Office	5	3.521	1.027	1.479
7.	Awareness of the jurisdiction for filing patent application in India	5	3.458	1.042	1.542
8.	Awareness of the withdrawal procedure of patent application	5	3.408	1.032	1.592

9.	Awareness of the types of applications available for patenting	5	3.415	1.042	1.585
10.	Awareness of the documents required for filing	5	3.419	1.060	1.581
11.	Awareness of fees , payment modes of fees for patenting	5	3.436	1.046	1.564
12.	Awareness of the meaning of provisional application and its procedure	5	3.440	1.049	1.56

Source: Computed Data

The mean score for “Awareness of how to apply for a patent” is 3.754 with a standard deviation of 1.010 and a gap of 1.246. This indicates that, on average, respondents have a moderate understanding of the process of applying for a patent.

The mean score for “Awareness of who can apply for a patent” is 3.587 with a standard deviation of 0.981 and a gap of 1.413. This suggests that respondents' awareness of who is eligible to apply for a patent is slightly lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of when should an application for a patent be filed” is 3.504 with a standard deviation of 1.032 and a gap of 1.496. This indicates that respondents' awareness of the timing for filing patent applications is moderately lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of online filing of patent application” is 3.462 with a standard deviation of 1.066 and a gap of 1.538. This suggests that respondents' awareness of online filing options for patent applications is below the ideal score.

The mean score for” Awareness of provision for filing patent application electronically” is 3.456 with a standard deviation of 1.062 and a gap of 1.544. This indicates that respondents' awareness of the provision for electronically filing patent applications is slightly lower than the ideal score, with a significant level of variability in responses. More information on electronic filing procedures may be helpful.

The mean score for “Awareness of the language by which an application for patent be filed with the Indian Patent Office” is 3.521 with a standard deviation of 1.027 and a gap of 1.479. This suggests that respondents' awareness of the language requirements for filing patent applications with the Indian Patent Office is moderately lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of the jurisdiction for filing patent application in India” is 3.458 with a standard deviation of 1.042 and a gap of 1.542. This indicates that respondents' awareness of the jurisdictional aspects of filing patent applications in India is slightly lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of the withdrawal procedure of patent application” is 3.408 with a standard deviation of 1.032 and a gap of 1.592. This suggests that respondents' awareness of the withdrawal procedure for patent applications is moderately lower than the ideal score

The mean score for “Awareness of the types of applications available for patenting “ is 3.415 with a standard deviation of 1.042 and a gap of 1.585. This indicates that respondents' awareness of the available types of patent applications is slightly lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of the documents required for filing” is 3.419 with a standard deviation of 1.060 and a gap of 1.581. This suggests that respondents' awareness of the required documents for filing patent applications is slightly lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of fees, payment modes of fees for patenting” is 3.436 with a standard deviation of 1.046 and a gap of 1.564. This indicates that respondents' awareness of patenting fees and payment methods is slightly lower than the ideal score.

The mean score for “Awareness of the meaning of provisional application and its procedure” is 3.440 with a standard deviation of 1.049 and a gap of 1.560. This suggests that respondents' awareness of provisional patent applications and their procedures is slightly lower than the ideal score.

Conclusion

The analysis of the patent awareness levels among students reveals significant gaps across various critical aspects of the patenting process. Despite an ideal score of 5, indicating full awareness, the mean scores for all variables range between 3.408 and 3.754, highlighting substantial knowledge deficits. Specifically, the highest awareness was observed in understanding how to apply for a patent (mean score 3.754, SD 1.010), yet it still falls short by 1.246 points. Conversely, the lowest awareness pertained to the withdrawal procedure of a patent application (mean score 3.408, SD 1.032), with a gap of 1.592 points. Other critical areas such as the timing of patent applications, online filing procedures, jurisdiction, and the types of applications available also exhibit notable gaps, suggesting that students lack comprehensive

understanding and practical knowledge about the patenting process. This overall lack of awareness indicates a need for enhanced education and training in intellectual property (IP) within academic curricula to better prepare students for engaging with the patent system effectively.

Suggestions

1. **Integrate Comprehensive IP Education into Curricula:**

- Academic institutions should incorporate detailed courses on intellectual property rights, specifically focusing on the patenting process. This could be included in the syllabus of engineering, technology, and business programs to ensure students understand the practical aspects of applying for patents.

2. **Organize Workshops and Seminars:**

- Regular workshops and seminars conducted by IP professionals can provide students with hands-on experience and up-to-date information on patent application procedures, electronic filing, and other relevant topics. Interactive sessions could address specific areas where awareness is particularly low.

3. **Develop Online Resources and Tutorials:**

- Creating online modules, video tutorials, and interactive guides on the patenting process can serve as valuable resources for students. These should cover each aspect of the patent process, including application procedures, jurisdiction, and fee structures, and be accessible to all students.

4. **Encourage Participation in IP Competitions and Projects:**

- Institutions can encourage students to participate in IP-related competitions, hackathons, and projects. These activities can provide practical experience and motivate students to engage deeply with the patenting process.

5. **Collaborate with Patent Offices:**

- Establish partnerships with national patent offices to facilitate internships, mentorship programs, and guest lectures. Direct interaction with patent examiners and IP attorneys can offer students insights into the practical challenges and nuances of the patent system.

6. Enhance Faculty Training:

- Faculty members should be provided with training and resources to effectively teach IP and patent-related topics. This ensures that educators are well-equipped to guide students through the complexities of the patenting process.

7. Implement Feedback Mechanisms:

- Regular feedback and assessment mechanisms should be established to evaluate the effectiveness of IP education initiatives. Surveys and focus groups can help identify persistent gaps in knowledge and adjust educational strategies accordingly.

By adopting these suggestions, academic institutions can significantly improve patent awareness among students, preparing them to better navigate the IP landscape and contribute to innovation and economic development.

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